

SIGNIFICANCE OF PRANAYAMA ON PERCEIVED MENTAL HEALTH: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF AGED

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ABSTRACT

The present study was intended to see the significance of Pranayama on perceived mental health among aged. It is often seen that in the present day, fast changing scenario of human life where each and every individual faces different kinds of sources of stress which affects mental health of the individual directly or indirectly both, not only in India but through out the globe. It is generally viewed that mental health is a state of well-being in which individual realizes his/her own abilities to cope with the normal stresses of life. Thus, the present researchers tried to know about those regular practices especially Pranayama – a kind of yoga which may contribute an individual especially aged in progression towards the positive mental health. For the present study sixty aged (N=60) were selected which comprises male (n=30) and female (n=30) from rural areas of Madhubani district. A Pranayama centre was temporarily established at our private home for the period of fifteen days. Initially, mental health of both the group was checked using mental health questionnaire and individual scores were summed up and kept it confidential for statistical treatment. Then thereafter 15 days regular practices of Pranayama were demonstrated among all aged irrespective of sex, caste and religion with the help of yoga trainer. After 15 days regular Pranayama, mental health was checked again using questionnaire. After analyzing the obtained data, it has been found that Pranayama – a kind of yoga helps to maintain the over all mental health of aged. It is very interesting to note that female aged group differs in terms of their perceived reactions on mental health from male aged especially from where the present sample has been drawn for the present piece of research enquiry. Finding of the study has been discussed in detail by highlighting the probable reasons.

Key-Words: Pranayama, Mental Health, Aged, Male, Female, Empirical Study

INTRODUCTION

Changing human life sphere causes many psychological problems especially with regard to mental health. In fact mental health is a psychological state of well-being, characterized by continuing personal growth, a sense of purpose in life, self-acceptance, and positive relations

with others. Many social scientists define mental health as the absence of mental illness, but many psychologists consider this definition too narrow. Thus, mental health can also refer to a field of study encompassing both mental health and mental illness.

It is true that a large number of distinct dimensions of mental health have been identified by psychologists and other behavioral scientists. These include self-acceptance, or self-esteem, characterized by a positive evaluation of oneself and one's past experiences; personal growth reflected in one's sense of continued psychological growth and development; a sense that one's life has purpose and meaning; positive relations with others; environmental mastery, the capacity to manage effectively in the surrounding world; and autonomy, a sense of self-determination and the ability to control one's own life. Self-acceptance, relations with others, environmental mastery, and autonomy usually improve as a person ages and gains life experience. Though, many people find that their personal growth and sense of purpose in life begin to decline in midlife.

Many psychologists viewed mental health as the ability to maintain a balance between positive and negative emotions, such as joy and sadness. Other psychologists emphasize the role of one's environment in influencing well-being. This perspective sees mental health reflected in a person's overall happiness with various domains of life, such as social relationships, work, and community.

Surgeon General's report focused for the first time on mental health rather than physical health. In his report, mental health was defined as "a state of successful performance of mental function, resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships with people, and the ability to adapt to change and to cope with adversity" (U.S. Public Health Service, 1999, p. 4). In 2004, the World Health Organization's historic first report on mental health promotion defined mental health as: a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community (World Health Organization, 2004). In contrast, mental disorder (synonymous with *mental illness*) is a persistent deviation from normal functioning that is sufficient to cause emotional suffering and role impairment, diminishing individuals' capacities to execute their responsibilities as a parent, spouse, or employee (WHO, 2003). Although it sounds serious, and its name equates it with physical illness, mental illness was not considered a priority by the medical and public health community until the last decade of the twentieth century. Health is an essential aspect of human life. It is well-recognized truth from the time immemorial that possessing good health is pre-requisite for every human being for all-round growth and development. The word "Mental" means "of the mind". It describes our thoughts, feelings and understanding of ourselves and the world around us. The word "health" generally describes the working order of our body and mind. So, that when we talk about mental health we refer it to the working order of an individual's mind.

Mental health, however, is a contested and still much debated concept, with no universally accepted definition (Herron et.al, 2000; Friedli, 2004). In fact, it has been argued that there can be no universally accepted definition (Herron et.al, 2000; Warr, 1987) due to the fact that mental

health is multi-dimensional and value-laden. A wide range of meanings and definitions exist amongst individuals, reflecting, for example, differences in terms of age, sex, socio-cultural contexts, experiences, and lack of common language. Additionally, interpretations are dynamic and mental health is often used interchangeably with, emotional, psychological and subjective well-being. Thus, no definition is ideal or without problems and mental health is more complex and subjective than any definition in this regard.

Mental health is often defined as a state of well being in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully and is able to make a contribution to her or his community. The World Health Organization defines mental health as "a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully and is able to make a contribution to his or her community" (WHO, 2005). Boehm (1955) says that the condition and level of mental health should be socially acceptable. According to Charandas (1986) mental health is the adjustment of human being to the world and to each other with maximum of effectiveness and happiness. It is an important aspect of one's total health. From perspectives of the discipline of positive psychology mental health may include an individual's ability to enjoy life and procure a balance between life activities and efforts to achieve psychological resilience.

One of the distinguished scholars, viz., Weare (2004) is of the personal opinion that mental health is getting its deeper concern with some important positive characteristics of the individual such as: resilience and an inner sense of coherence; the ability to make relationships, to attach to others and to love the ability to think clearly including emotional matters; the ability to manage the emotions successfully and appropriately; the ability to be sensitive to one's own and other's emotions; and the capacity to have an accurate self concept and high self-esteem.

A moment ago the field of Global Mental Health has emerged, and defined as 'the area of study, research and practice that places a priority on improving mental health and achieving equity in mental health for all people worldwide' (Patel and Prince, 2010).

The term mental health has been classified into two different broader categories known as positive and negative mental health. Mental health from the positive angle refers to behavior, attitudes and feeling that respect an individual's level of personal effectiveness, success and satisfaction. Argyris (1951) suggested that persons with positive mental health should have the ability to understand the realities which exists both externally and internally when he/she strives to be aware of their one self. Buck (1972) found that employees who reported working under pressure indicated decreased mental health. Emmons (1992) viewed that mentally healthy persons are able to fulfill their social roles successfully. They enjoy peace of mind, happiness, self confidence and others' companionship. Negative mental health covers a wide variety of deep feelings including sorrow, disappointment, anger and empathy etc. O'Neil and others (1985) found that stress in the work environment has a negative impact on the physical and mental

health of working women. Nagaratnamma (1999) says that employees of different organizations differ with regards to their mental health. According to Johns et al. (1989) mental health is a condition which is characteristics of the average person who meets the demands of life on the basis of his own capacities and limitations.

It is also important to point out that mental illness refer to all diagnosable mental disorders, it is in fact that mental disorders are health conditions that are characterized by alterations in thinking, mood or behavior (or some combinations thereof) associated with distress and/or impaired functioning (Goyal, 1997).

An important study conducted over last forty years on the prevalence of mental disorders in India by Ganguli (2000) suggested that 73 persons have mental disorders in a population of 1000 persons. Similarly, Sharma and Singh (2001) revealed that in the state of Goa the prevalence rate of mental disorder was 60%, more among males as compare to females and likewise it was found much higher among Christians as compared to Hindus; but it was found very much similar in urban and rural areas. Recently, Zilli and Ali (2009) have conducted a study on mental health among players and non-players. The findings of the study revealed significant difference between players and non-players on mental health dimensions. Similarly, Zilli et.al (2009) concluded that female youth scored higher on mental health dimensions as compared to their male counterparts.

Mental health is the launch pad of thinking, communication skills, learning, emotional growth, resilience and self steam. It is how people look at themselves, their lives and the other people in their lives; evaluate their challenges and problems; and explores choices. This includes handling stress, relating to other people and making decisions. A study conducted by Sanadnarj et al. (1988) to see the relationship between physical health and mental health among 260 male and 252 females and they found that those who enjoy good physical health are most likely to have better mental health as compare to those who are suffering from poor mental health.

Having reviewed extensive review of literature on the mental health, none of the studies had been found on the significance of Pranayama – a kind of yoga in relation to mental health especially on the sample area from where the present piece of research work has been carried out, hence, the present study is of utmost value and will fill the void of knowledge in the area concerned.

\OBJECTIVES OF THE PRESENT STUDY

Thus, the present study was aimed to see the significance of Pranayama on perceived reactions of mental health. Pranayama is an important kind of yoga which helps individual to become balance, physically and mentally both. It is important to be mentioned that the word ‘yoga’ is derived from the Sanskrit word ‘yuj’ meaning to unite, to join, or to connect. It is the joining of a healthy physique and a disciplined mind for spiritual development. The preliminary objective of yoga is to improve body, health and physical abilities. It is through physical soundness and stability that mental powers can be achieved. In a nutshell yoga is an ancient Indian way of life that includes the practice of asana (certain postures), Pranayama (regulated breathing) and

Vipassana (meditation). On the other hand, mental health is generally described as that state in the interrelationship of the individual and his environment in which the personality is relatively stable and the environmental stressors are within its absorption capacity.

Having reviewed extensive survey of literature on the study of mental health in relation to Pranayama, it has been observed that none of the studies are available on the problem pertaining to aged men and women with reference to Madhubani district, India, hence, the present study is of immense value which will fill the void of knowledge in the area concerned. As it is generally assumed that men and women differ to each other in respect of their physical values, mental values and in their problems, therefore, the present investigation was planned to study mental health in relation to Pranayama among aged men and aged women with particular reference to Madhubani district, India.

HYPOTHESES

In the light of the broad objectives of the present study the following hypotheses were formulated:

1. Aged male will have better mental health as compare to female aged on over all mental health inventory before the Pranayama – a kind of yoga.
2. None of the dimensions of mental health will have significant difference between the group of aged male and female before the session Pranayama.
3. After 15 days regular practices of Pranayama aged female will have better mental health from aged male comparatively.
4. After 15 days regular practices of Pranayama there will be no significant difference between the group of aged male and female in terms of various dimensions of mental health.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sample: Total sample of the present Study consisted of (N=60) elderly people who were attain the age of 60 +, comprising male (n=30) and female (n=30) which were selected from different rural locality of Madhubani district – a well known town of North Bihar.

Tools used: The following measures were used in the present piece of research work.

1. **Mental Health Inventory:** For measuring mental health of the school teachers a standardized mental health inventory developed by Jagdish and Srivastava (2003) was used. Inventory consisted of 56 items, including 24 negative and 32 positive and having a lowest score of 56 and highest score of 224. Since the neutral point is at 140, scores below 140 indicate poor mental health while scores above 140 reflect good mental health. Each item of the inventory was rated on 4 point rating scale ranging from always to never with a score of 1 to 4. Inventory comprises of six dimensions such as, Positive self-evaluation (PSE), Perception of reality (PR), Integration of personality (IP), Autonomy (Autonomy), Group-oriented attitudes (GOA), and Environmental Mastery (EM).

2. **Biographical Information Blank (BIB):** Biographical Information Blank (BIB) was also prepared by the present investigators and used for analyzing the obtained results. Information included in it was like age, income, type of family, number of dependents, qualifications, etc.

Procedure:

These two materials were in printed form and were administered on each and every aged male and female before beginning of the Pranayama for which a Pranayama centre was established at our private home for the period of 15 days. Initially, mental health of both the group was checked using mental health questionnaire schedule along with biographical information. Individual scores were summed up on the items of mental health inventory and kept it confidential for statistical treatment. Then thereafter 15 days regular practices of Pranayama were demonstrated among all aged irrespective of sex, caste and religion with the help of yoga trainer. After 15 days regular practices of Pranayama, mental health was checked again using questionnaire schedule.

The responses were scored again according to the procedure and the individual scores were obtained. Having obtained the data, both the data (before and after Pranayama) were tabulated for giving statistical treatment for obtaining the results and presented in tables. Finally, the results were discussed and the formulated hypotheses were tested.

Results and Discussions:

Before Pranayama Session

Table: 1 Showing Comparative Difference between the group of male and female aged on their levels of perceived Mental Health before the session of Pranayama

Levels	Group of Male Aged (n=30)		Group of Female Aged (n=30)	
	n	Percentages	n	Percentages
High	05	16.67 %	07	23.33 %
Moderate	15	50 %	17	56.67 %
Low	10	33.33 %	06	20%

As the obtained result presented in Table- 1 also reveals the clear cut picture regarding the levels of perceived reactions of aged male and female on the degree of mental health before the session of Pranayama. As it could be seen from the table-1, 23.33% aged female of Madhubani district of North Bihar had shown higher degree of mental health than aged male in the same district i.e. 16.67%. It is also evident from the table, 50% of aged male from the same district have been found possessing moderate level of mental health than aged female i.e. 56.67% which is comparatively higher in percentage, whereas, 20% aged female had low degree of mental health which is comparatively lesser than their aged male counterpart i.e. 33.33%. The obtained results presented in the table – 1 can also be observed by the following chart.

Table - 2 Showing Mean, SD and t-values Between the Group of Aged Female and Aged Male of Madhubani District on Overall Mental Health Inventory And Dimensions-Wise before Pranayama Session

Dimensions	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	P*
Overall mental health	Female	177.4	13.2	2.80	< .01
	Male	168.1	12.11		
Positive self evaluation	Female	32.5	2.76	6.51	< .01
	Male	28.2	2.30		
Perception of reality	Female	23.6	1.87	6.96	< .01
	Male	20.4	1.67		
Integration of personality	Female	33.5	4.29	1.13	NS
	Male	32.3	3.78		
Autonomy	Female	16.7	1.65	3.57	< .01
	Male	15.2	1.64		
Group oriented attitude	Female	28.8	3.12	1.22	NS
	Male	27.7	3.72		
Environmental mastery	Female	26.6	2.73	2.00	< .05
	Male	25.3	2.24		

In continuation of the obtained results presented in Table- 2 clearly indicates that in the case of aged female group the mean and SD was found to be 177.4 and 13.2, while in the case of aged male group the Mean and SD was found to be 168.1 and 12.11 respectively, which is statistically significant at 0.01 level as t – value has been found 2.80. Thus, the result proves the present underlying major hypothesis of our present piece of research work that “Aged male would have better mental health as compare to female aged on over all mental health inventory”., stands rejected.

Table 2 clearly indicated that in the case of aged female group on different dimensions of mental health the means values has been found high than their male counterparts, hence, out of six four dimensions of mental health, viz., positive self evaluation, perception of reality, autonomy, and environmental mastery has been found statistically significant as their t – values are 6.51, 6.96, 3.57, 2.0 respectively. By obtaining such type of results, hypothesis formulated i.e. ‘none of the dimensions of mental health will have significant difference between the group of aged male and female also stand rejected especially from where the present piece of research work has been carried out. The obtained results seems to be logical in the sense that only mental health was measured without any demonstration of yoga, hence, subjects reported their feelings on the items of mental health questionnaire schedule freely but significant difference between the group has been statistically found. Moreover, general assumption in the Indian society is that the male figure is responsible to organize all activities related to cater the needs of the family, thus, aged female had reported better mental health than male counterpart.

The results obtained and presented in table No. 2 on total dimension of mental health which clearly highlight the facts that aged female are getting sound mental health as compared to aged male due to high conducive socio-cultural milieu with lower level life stressful situations. A number of studies conducted by Buck (1972), Taimini (1986), Nagaratnamma (1999), Kuttner, et al. (2006), Ahmad (2013) and Pandey (2014) they extend their whole support to present findings pertaining to mental health of the people.

AFTER 15 DAYS REGULAR PRACTICES OF PRANAYAMA SESSION

Table: 3 Showing Comparative Difference between the Group of Male and Female aged on their levels of Perceived Mental Health after Pranayama Session

Levels	Group of Female Aged (n=30)		Group of Male Aged (n=30)	
	n	Percentages	n	Percentages
High	10	33.33 %	08	26.67 %
Moderate	16	53.33 %	14	46.67 %
Low	04	13.33 %	08	26.66 %

As the results presented in Table- 3 also depicts the picture pertaining to the levels of perceived reactions of aged male and female on their degree of mental health after 15 days regular practices of Pranayama session. It could be observed from the table-3, 33.33 % aged female of Madhubani district of North Bihar had shown higher degree of mental health than aged male i.e. 26.67 %. It is also evident from the table, 53.33 % of aged female had reported possessing moderate level of mental health than aged male i.e. 46.67 % which is comparatively lower in percentage, whereas, 13.33% aged female had low degree of mental health which is comparatively lesser than their aged male counterpart i.e. 26.66 %. The hypothesis formulated i.e. ‘after 15 days regular practices of Pranayama, aged female will have better mental health from aged male comparatively’, stands accepted. The Obtained results presented in the table – 3 with regard to comparative difference between the group of aged female and aged male in the extent of perceived mental health after the 15 days regular practices of Pranayama session can also be observed by the following chart.

The results presented in table – 3 which is witnessed from the table – 4 where it can also be observed that after 15 days regular practices of Pranayama – a kind of yoga, mental health of the aged female has been found more better than aged male as the mean value – 181.4 of female was found high in comparison to aged male i.e. 175.3 but it is very interesting to point out that when ‘t’ was analyzed then thereafter no significant difference had been found between the group of aged female and male with regard to mental health. It shows the significance of Pranayama on mental health of aged (male and female).

Table - 4 showing mean, SD and t-values between the group of aged female and aged male of Madhubani district on overall mental health scores and Dimension-wise after Pranayama session

Dimensions	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	P*
Overall mental health	Female	181.4	18.12	1.30	NS
	Male	175.3	17.56		
Positive self evaluation	Female	32.5	2.87	1.62	NS
	Male	31.4	2.30		
Perception of reality	Female	23.3	1.79	1.08	NS
	Male	22.8	1.75		
Integration of personality	Female	34.2	3.76	0.36	NS
	Male	33.8	4.62		
Autonomy	Female	16.6	1.67	0.39	NS
	Male	16.8	1.60		
Group oriented attitude	Female	30.1	3.15	1.65	NS
	Male	28.6	3.76		
Environmental mastery	Female	27.7	2.73	2.05	< .05
	Male	26.3	2.45		

In continuation of the table – 3, it could also be observed from the table - 4 that out of various dimensions of mental health inventory, only ‘environmental mastery’ – a dimension of mental health has been found as the significant difference between aged female and aged male at .05 level of confidence as the data obtained after 15 days regular practices of Pranayama – a kind of yoga. The obtained results seem to be logical; it is because of the fact that the degree to which there are inequalities in the probabilities of major life events to occur to different social groups in terms of their life happiness. In other words, we can say that the degree to which people compare themselves most with their near equals in a society or peer groups will affect the relative impact of different life events upon happiness that’s why ‘environmental mastery’ a dimension of

mental health has been emerged as significant difference between the group after the 15 days of regular practices of Pranayama. In addition, it is important to be mentioned that to increase or maintain the active mobility of older people pertaining to better mental health community planning strategies and community amenities are important to minimize environmental and social barriers to ensure equal opportunities in the society. Most of the aged either males or females reported that they feel better now after Pranayama session and enforced to be continue. Moreover, it is also important to be mentioned that aged people irrespective of caste, class, sex and religion should be given opportunities to participate in physical activities such as Asana, Pranayama, Vipassana, etc. It should help the elderly for maintaining over all mental health in the direction of their happy life.

CONCLUSIONS

In the light of the results obtained and its interpretations the important conclusions are summed up below:

1. Aged female has been found to have better mental health before the demonstration of Pranayama than their male counterpart.
2. Significance of difference has been found between the group of aged female and male on their degree of perceived mental health before starting the session of Pranayama.
3. Out of six dimensions of mental health three dimensions viz., ‘positive self evaluation’, ‘perception of reality’, ‘autonomy’ and ‘environmental mastery’ have been found possessing significant difference between the group of aged female and male before the session of Pranayama.
4. After 15 days regular practices of Pranayama – a kind of yoga aged female were found more prone to have better mental health than their male counterpart.
5. No significant difference has been found on over all mental health inventories after 15 days regular practices of Pranayama between the group of aged female and male, although, both the group had shown positive inclination towards better mental health.
6. Having completed the 15 days regular practices of Pranayama – a kind of yoga, ‘environmental mastery’ – a dimension of mental has been found possessing significant difference between the group of aged female and male, although, both the group have shown quite favorable inclination towards their sound mental health.
7. Observations have revealed the fact that there is a need to pay much more attention to the necessities of aged people by providing better mental health community planning strategies and community amenities which are important to minimize environmental and social barriers to ensure equal opportunities in the society. Moreover, it is also important to be mentioned that aged people irrespective of caste, class, sex and religion should have opportunities to participate in physical activities. Physical exercise classes such as Asana, Pranayama, Vipassana, etc should be adapted to the possible special needs of elderly irrespective of sex for maintaining over all mental health by opening a yoga centre especially for aged. Indeed sound mental health is the need of the hour in general and in all walks of life to make congenial environment within Indian socio-cultural milieu.

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